

PLEP-0007 – Structure of Top-Level Sub-Packages

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Abstract

This PLEP defines the top-level structure of PlasmaPy (i.e. `plasmapy.<subpackage>`). Its intent is to name the top-level sub-packages and define the general scope of each package. Sub-package details are left to be defined in package focused PLEPs, which should *NOT* conflict with this PLEP. Defining the top-level structure should:

1. keep the top-level namespace from getting bloated

2. help developers decide where new code should be placed
3. help navigate users to the functionality they need

If new code does NOT fall within the current framework after a thorough and exhaustive review, then this PLEP needs to be modified/updated accordingly before any new top-level sub-packages are created.

Detailed Description

Why?

By defining the top-level sub-package namespace developers are better directed to where code should be added, the [PlasmaPy Coordinating Committee](#) can better manage package bloat, and users are better directed to the code they need.

Top-Level Sub-Packages

The following sub-packages are outlined in this PLEP, with brief synopses given in the tables below. The details of each package are left to be fully defined by their respective package PLEPs.

1. [addons](#)
2. [analysis](#)
3. [diagnostics](#)
4. [dispersion](#)
5. [formulary](#)
6. [particles](#)
7. [plasma](#)
8. [simulation](#)
9. [tests](#)
10. [utils](#)

addons

directory: `./plasmapy/addons/`
access: `plasmapy.addons`
PLEP:

addons

scope: The `addons` sub-package is intended to be a plugin location to allow 3rd party users to extend the capabilities of `PlasmaPy`.

`PlasmaPy`'s primary goal is to provide common functionality to the plasma community as a whole and avoids getting too focused on resources/functionality that are specific to a research group, instrument, laboratory, etc. However, we do see the benefit of having this functionality available in the `PlasmaPy` ecosystem. This `addons` entry point allows for the `PlasmaPy` community to develop separate open-source distributions that extend the functionality of `plasmapy`.

Note:

Extending `PlasmaPy` by adding to `plasmapy.addons` will be covered in a future PLEP.

analysis

directory: `./plasmapy/analysis/`

access: `plasmapy.analysis`

PLEP:

scope: A sub-package focused on providing analysis techniques that can be applied to data collected from a variety of sources (simulation, experimental, space, etc.).

The focus of an analysis routine should be made as broad as possible. When the routine's functionality becomes highly-tailored to its application, then it should be placed into an explicitly appropriate namespace. For example, `linear`, `langmuir`, `magnetic-flux`, etc. analysis tools should be placed in their respective namespaces within `plasmapy.analysis`.

diagnostics

directory: `./plasmapy/diagnostics/`

access: `plasmapy.diagnostics`

PLEP:

diagnostics

scope: A sub-package that fully defines the parameters of a "diagnostic." A "diagnostic" is any data collecting instrument ranging from experimental probes, like Langmuir and magnetic flux probes, to analogous synthetic diagnostics for simulations.

Tools in this package do not define any analysis routines, but focus on defining probe characteristics/calibrations that can be seamlessly passed to `plasmapy.analysis` routines.

A "Diagnostic" class should fully define its diagnostic characteristics and provide access to its most relevant analysis tools found in `plasmapy.analysis`.

dispersion

directory: `./plasmapy/dispersion/`

access: `plasmapy.dispersion`

PLEP:

scope: A sub-package containing tools to work with plasma dispersion relations. This includes, but is not limited to, solving dispersion relations, defining dispersion functions, plotting dispersion relations, etc.

formulary

directory: `./plasmapy/formulary/`

access: `plasmapy.formulary`

PLEP:

scope: A sub-package that provides mathematical and scientific formulas for calculating physical parameters of various plasmas. This is inspired by, and akin to, the [NRL Plasma Formulary](#).

particles

directory: `./plasmapy/particles/`

access: `plasmapy.particles`

PLEP:

particles

scope: A sub-package that fully defines the properties of a "particle." A "particle" can come in many forms ranging from a traditional particle (electron, ion, atom, etc.) to more exotic types like dust particles, dimensionless particles for simulations, super-particles for simulations, etc.

plasma

directory: `./plasmapy/plasma/`

access: `plasmapy.plasma`

PLEP:

scope: A sub-package that fully defines a plasma. This would include the plasma's species constituents and physical parameters (like temperature, boundary conditions, magnetic fields, distribution functions, etc.).

Any tools that go into defining a plasma or its environment (e.g. a field solver) should be included in a sub-package within `plasmapy.plasma`.

simulation

directory: `./plasmapy/simulation/`

access: `plasmapy.simulation`

PLEP:

scope: A sub-package focused on interfacing with simulations and/or running simulations.

If a new feature falls under the scope of the `analysis` and/or `diagnostics` sub-packages, then the new feature should be included in one of those sub-packages. For example, a synthetic diagnostic should be included in the `plasmapy.diagnostics` sub-package.

tests

directory: `./plasmapy/tests/`

access: `plasmapy.tests`

PLEP:

tests

scope: A collection of tests for top-level modules (i.e. functions and classes defined in top-level `.py` files).

Note:

Utilities associated with running and developing tests (e.g. "pytest helpers") should also be included here over `plasma.py.utils`.

utils

directory: `./plasma.py/utils/`

access: `plasma.py.utils`

PLEP:

scope: A collection of "utility" functions and classes to help us write (what we try to think of as) clean, readable, and informative code.

This collection does not provide any physics tools, instead it is focused on providing package development tools.

Note:

Utilities focused on running and developing tests should be placed in `plasma.py.tests` instead.

Extensible Packages are Exempt

Any package separately distributed from `plasma.py` does not need to go through a PLEP-7 review to add a top-level package to `plasma.py`. For example, a `plasma.py-foo` distribution does not require a PLEP-7 review to create the extensible sub-package `plasma.py.foo`. The reasoning here is (1) this top-level sub-package `plasma.py.foo` is not distributed with the main `plasma.py` package and (2) any user is purposefully installing the extensible package `plasma.py-foo`.

Implementation

Implementing this PLEP requires creation of new sub-packages and refactoring (renaming and/or moving) of existing modules and sub-packages into the outlined structure.

Implementation of this PLEP was started during the development of `plasma.py v0.3.0`.

Issues, Pull Requests, and Branches

All issues and pull requests were managed under the GitHub project [PLEP-0007 Implementation](#). The key pull requests were:

- [PR #692](#): "plasmapy.formulary - reshuffle"
- [PR #742](#): "Rename plasmapy.atomic to plasmapy.particles"
- [PR #728](#): "Refactor pytest helper functionality"

Backward Compatibility

This PLEP will NOT maintain backward compatibility.

Decision Rationale

Defining a top-level namespace for `plasmapy` will (1) prevent namespace pollution, (2) help guide developers on where to place new code, and (3) help navigate users to the functionality they need.